

SCIENTIFIC APPROACH FOR THE CLINICAL UNDERSTANDING OF BHAGANDARA

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ABSTRACT

Bhagandara has been described in detail in ayurvedic classics but its description is mainly based on clinical symptoms. This condition closely resembles with Fistula in ano. Its pictorial presentations are not very much available. In the present paper emphasis has been made to understand the different types of Fistula in ano with pictorial and radiological presentations. These radiological pictures have been obtained in our department during routine imaging of cases of Fistula in ano.

Key words: Bhagandara, Fistula in ano, Sushruta, Shatponaka, Ushtragreeva, Parisravi, Shambukavarta, Unmargi, Arshobhagandara

INTRODUCTION

Bhagandara : In ayurvedic classics disease described under the title of Bhagandara is closely similar to the fistula in ano in clinical appearance. Therefore Bhagandara is correlated with the fistula in ano.

Definition: Many references are available with description of Bhagandara, which expresses almost same meaning as per clinical presentation of the disease. According to the Sushruta, Bhagandara is the condition which produces darana (tear) of bhaga (perineum), guda (anus) and vasti (urinary bladder region). He also pointed out that, when the swelling is in un-suppurated stage it is called Bhagandara Pidika and when it bursts open, called Bhagandara. In this way the Bhagandara does not include fistula in ano only but it also incorporates the fistulae of bhaga (yoni), vasti (bladder) and perineum.

Bhagandara does not only indicate the scientific disease fistula in ano, but the clinical picture of this condition as described in the ayurvedic literature clearly suggests that

Bhagandara is the group of fistulae or separate fistula occurring in anus, vagina, perineum and urinary bladder region.

The ancient literature including Vedas, have detailed description of disease, their preventive and curative measures. The name 'Durum' has been correctly used by 'Vedic physician' for the disease of ano rectum. This has been widely accepted that the disease of Guda is more difficult to treat. Sushruta has devoted some chapters to describe methodology of diagnosis and treatment of this disease. Vagbhata also described this problem and made several improvements in its treatment. The earliest description of Bhagandara was given in 1000 B.C. by Sushruta, the father of Indian surgery, whereas before Sushruta we do not find much about this disease in the available ayurvedic literature. Charka has made a very short and passing reference to Bhagandara. After Sushruta his successors gave much importance to it and made their own contribution and quoted Sushruta. From the period of Sushruta the disease of Bhagandara has been considered very complicated diseases. He described eight grave diseases (mahagada) out of which Bhagandara is one. In the nidan chapter, Sushruta again mentioned that all types of Bhagandara are serious disease giving much trouble to the patient. Further he had mentioned that the Bhagandara becomes incurable when flatus, fecal matter, urine, sperms and worms pass through the external opening of Bhagandara.

Name Bhagandara is also called because in it the bhaga or perineal region and vasti or bladder are injured or involved. It is a sinus/ fistula, which has got an external opening or an internal opening in the ano rectal canal or both. The derivation of Bhagandara is "Bhagam Darayati Bhagandara". In this condition vagina, bladder, rectum any one of them or two or all of them may be injured, resulting in passing of feces, urine, flatus etc. the meaning of bhaga is often limited to reproductive organ i. e. vagina only. The name Bhaga asthi means the bone which internally occupies the vagina, bladder and rectum. Bhaga is not only used for vagina but it also covers all the three structures situated in the perineal region viz. vagina, urinary bladder (vasti) and ano rectal canal (guda). Darana gives two senses splitting and pain. Some authorities have mentioned a different sense of the word Darana which means an opening or in canal or a cave. Thus it can ultimately be inferred that the word, Bhagandara is a combination of two separate words i.e. bhaga and a darana which have been derived from the separate roots. Thus Bhagandara words it-self occupies a wide range which comes under the anal fistulae and all other vaginal, vesicle and urethral sinus/fistulae.

AETIOLOGY OF BHAGANDARA

According to Charka : Krimi roga, excessive coitus, foreign body infection in Gudamarga, straining during defecation, sitting in wrong posture and horse riding.

According to Vagbhata : Riding an elephant and horse, sitting in an uncomfortable position for long time, abusing the saints.

According to Bhawa prakash : Obesity produces boil and may result in Bhagandara.

According to Sushruta: Pidika when bursts open will lead to formation of fistula in ano.

According to Ayurvedic concepts all the disease are based on the process of dosha dushya samurchhana (interaction between body tissue and pathogen). Among all the Mahagadas (i.e., incurable diseases) Bhagandara has been considered as more troublesome condition. The tridoshas and dushya i.e. Rakta, Mamsa and Medas, are the causative factors

in pathogenesis of this disease. The prodromal features are formation of boil (i.e. Pidika), which bursts open after suppuration and forms the Bhagandara. Boil undergoes amavastha, pachyamanaavstha and pakavasatha to become fistula, in combination of tridhosha (i.e. Vata, Pitta, Kapha). Sometimes due to its inability to burst open outside, it gets open into neighboring structures and forms blind external sinus (antaramukhi Bhagandara). Vagbhatta described special characters of pidika which lead to Bhagandara.

PATHOGENESIS OF BHAGANDARA

Nidan	:	Mithaya ahara and vihara
Pradhana dosh	:	Pitta, Kapha
Dushya	:	Mamsa, Rakta
Adhithana	:	Guda

CLASSIFICATION OF BHAGANDARA

Shataponaka

- *Multiple opening usually superficial*
- *Thin frothy and abundant discharge.*
- *Pricking or cutting type of pain.*
- *Blackish or reddish discoloration.*

Ushtragreeva

- *Tiny and raised opening.*
- *Offensive and warm discharge.*
- *Burning pain.*
- *Reddish discoloration.*

Parisravi

- *Firm or indurations opening.*
- *Thick and sticky discharge.*
- *Itching pain.*
- *Whitish discoloration.*

Shambukavarta

- *Situated on posterior aspect of the anal canal.*
- *It is likely to communicate with urinary bladder or urethra.*
- *Mixed color discharge.*
- *May or may not open into rectum.*
- *Large and raised openings.*
- *Pricking, burning or itching pain coming at intervals.*

Unmargi

- *Multiple openings.*
- *Presence of impacted foreign body in the wound.*
- *Presence of worms or maggots in the wound.*

As per Sushruta : Nidan Sthana

- *Shataponaka*

- Ushtragreeva
- Parisravi
- Shambukavarta
- Unmargi

As per Sushruta : Chikitsa Sthana

- Parachin-Bahirmukha
- Arvachin-antarmukha

As per Vagbhatta

- Vattaj pittaj
- Kapha Vattaj
- Pittaj kaphaja
- Sannipataj
- Agantuj
- Parikshepi
- Riju
- Arshobhagandara

Sushruta and Vagbhatta have mentioned types of blind fistulae as Bahir mukha and Antar mukha which can be considered as external and internal blind fistula respectively. Clinically Parikshepi travels around the anal canal thus similar to the complete horse shoe fistulae. Straight tract opening directly into rectum resembles Parisravi. Bhagandara with multiple external openings can be considered as Shataponaka Bhagandara. Bhagandara with large arched tracts may be considered as Ushtragreeva where as Bhagandara with circled or rounded tract can be considered as Shambukavarta. Bhagandara with long straight tracts may be denoted as Unmargi and Riju Bhagandara. Bhagandara occurring in association with haemorrhoids is known as Arshobhagandara.

Shataponaka Bhagandara : (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1 : Photograph showing (a) schematic representation Shataponaka Bhagandara (b) external appearance of the perianal region with multiple fistulous opening (c) Fistulogram showing multiple branches and external openings with internal opening and rectal communication.

Regarding the specific pathology described in ayurvedic classics. Shataponaka is produced by the predominance of vata. Due to indulgence in unprincipled diets and habits, the vayu gets vitiated and localized in the area of one to two fingers around the ano rectal

region. Which affects the dushya resulting into a reddish discoloration; in this condition patient have specific pain like prickling sensation and results into suppuration due to negligence of the treatments. The wound is always moist because it is closed proximity to the urinary bladder and clear or foamy discharges flows out continuously from the minute multiple holes. Then on negligence of treatment this turns into Shataponaka Bhagandara.

Ushtragreeva Bhagandara : (Fig. 2)

Fig. 2 : Photograph showing (a) schematic representation of Ushtragreeva Bhagandara (b) external perianal region with Ushtragreeva Bhagandara and (c) fistulogram with long curved camel neck like fistulous tract.

Regarding pathogenesis of Ushtragreeva Sushruta described that vitiated pitta is pushed downwards by the vayu causing accumulation and produces a red colored small and raised inflamed swelling like the neck of camels. It gives specific burning types of pain and results into suppuration. It gives rise to various symptoms and discharges if neglected. This type of Bhagandara is with more pittaj lakshanas than the other doshas.

Parisravi Bhagandara: (Fig. 3)

Fig. 3 : Photograph showing (a) schematic representation of Parisravi Bhagandara (b) external perianal region with Parisravi Bhagandara and (c) fistulogram with long fistulous tract with large cavity in pararectal area and rectal communication.

Pathogenesis of Parisravi is mainly due to vitiated khapa being directed downwards by the vayu, which gets accumulated causing Bhgandara resembling Ushtragreeva (neck of camel). It produces white colored firm swelling with itching. If untreated suppuration results and the resultant wound is indurated, usually associated with itching and a continuous mucoid discharge flows through, from it.

Shambukavarta Bhagandara :(Fig. 4)

Fig. 4 : Photograph showing (a) schematic representation of Shambukavarta Bhagandara (b) external perianal region with Shambukavarta Bhagandara and (c) fistulogram with circular and helical fistulous tract resembling conch shell (Shambuka).

Pathogenesis of Shambukavarta has been considered as result of vitiated tridoshas. The vitiated vayu is in close association with the vitiated pitta and kapha, which travels down and accumulates around the anus region resembling shape of ushtragreeva. This causes a swelling resembling tip of the great toe in external appearance, which ultimately results into a discharging wound.

Unmargi Bhagandara : (Fig. 5)

Fig. 5 : Photograph showing (a) schematic representation of Unmargi Bhagandara (b) external perianal region with Unmargi Bhagandara and (c) fistulogram with long straight fistulous tract resembling Unmargi Bhagandara.

The Unmargi Bhagandara is not produced by vitiation of doshas but has been said as Agantuj (due to external cause). In this type of Bhagandara firstly foreign body initiates disease process later on tridosha gets involved. It is quite opposite to above mentioned four types of bhagandara. Almost all Ayurvedic authors agree that this type of Bhagandara is produced by some trauma due to foreign body in the vicinity of anal canal or rectum.

Parikshepi Bhagandara (Fig. 6)

Fig. 6 : Photograph showing (a) schematic representation of Parikshepi Bhagandara (b) external perianal region with Parikshepi Bhagandara and (c) fistulogram with fistulous tract encircling the anal canal resembling Parikshepi Bhagandara.

Vitiated vata and pitta localize around the anal canal and produce a copper colored pidika. On suppuration a curved tract is formed all around the anal canal just as a trench is present all around the fort.

Riju Bhagandara: (Fig. 7)

Fig. 7 : Photograph showing (a) schematic representation of Riju Bhagandara (b) external perianal region with Riju Bhagandara and (c) fistulogram with long straight fistulous tract resembling Riju Bhagandar.

Vitiated vata and Kapha tear the anal canal producing a linear tract associated with severe pain.

Arshobhagandara (Fig. 8)

Fig. 8 : Photograph showing (a) schematic representation of Arshobhagandara (b) external perianal region with Arshobhagandara and (c) fistulogram with long internal opening, rectal communication and semi horse shoe tract. Hemorrhoids cannot be seen in fistulogram.

Vitiated kapha and pitta localizes at the base of an arsha, which is already present and gets aggravated, producing pain, burning and itching sensation. This localized swelling undergoes suppuration, leading to the formation of fistulous tract, below the arsha. Because of continuous discharge from the tract, the arsha always remains moist.

According to Sushruta when a bony foreign body present in the food, is forced down with solid stools by the apana vayu, then it causes trauma to the anal canal. In due course of time this injury gets infected by krimis and ultimately resulting into multiple sinuses. These organisms' eats away anus and causing tearing of anus from many sides.

Regarding Arshobhagandara its specific pathogenesis have been described clearly .vata, pitta, separately or two dosha, migrates into arsha, which is, present and produce itching, burning and swelling at the pedicle of the arsha mass. Then it suppurates, burst out and stuff comes out from various openings of sinus though the piles pedicles. Thus he had clear view that the infection of the anus due to inflammation of piles, may lead to Bhagandara. This Sushruta classification of Bhagandara is accepted by many ayurvedic scholars. The multiple tracts variety is known as Shataponaka, but the multiple fistulae are superficial course. Thus Shataponaka can be considered under subcutaneous or low anal group of fistulae in ano, whereas Ushtragreeva can be taken as rectal sinuses which have small opening on a raised epitheliased granulation tissue. This type will have curved tract with internal openings between the two bellies of the external sphincter or above the sphincter. Ushtragreeva considered under low anal or high anal can be compared to Parisravi, which is profusely discharging with large cavity inside. The ano rectal variety can be considered as Ushtragreeva, if it has a curved tract or Parisravi if it is having sinus with a

large cavity with pus in its root. The Shambukavarta can be considered as horse shoe type of fistulae. It exist at posterior side of the rectum, usually internal opening at 6'0clock position.

References:

1. Arun Tripathi, K. R. Sharma, Management of high rectal fistula with Ksahr sutra by M.D.(Ay.) thesis (1975-1976).
2. B D Chaurasia, Human Anatomy, 4th edition.
3. David Sutton; Text book of Radiology and Imaging Volume- 2.
4. G. Russel et al; Baileys & Loves short practice of surgery, 23rd edition.
5. S. Das, Text book of Surgery, 3rd edition.
6. K. Gangadharan, M. Sahu, Ph. D. thesis 2009 (BHU).